

The Impact of Psychological Empowerment Dimensions on Organizational Citizenship Behavior of Millennial Generation Workers

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to see the magnitude of the impact that the dimensions of psychological empowerment have on organizational citizenship behavior. The respondents were 100 generation Y workers in Indonesia obtained through convenience sampling. Data were analyzed using PLS SEM. The results show that the dimensions of competence and impact are able to increase OCB. The dimensions of meaning and self-determination have no impact on OCB. Future researchers can limit it to certain sectors such as public or private. This research contributes to increasing OCB through dimensions of psychological empowerment in millennial workers in Indonesia.

INTRODUCTION

In 2016, a survey institute called Gallup reported that six out of ten millennials often change jobs compared to older generations. The millennial generation (generation Y) has expectations of their superiors in the workplace in the form of stable communication and clearly defined expectations. The millennial generation is also reported to be less involved in their work and this has an impact on the economy. Work involvement itself has an impact on the level of organizational citizenship behavior of workers (Saxena & Saxena, 2015). The learning and development opportunities provided by organizations are important for the millennial generation when looking for a new job or staying employed at their current organization.

In 2023, a survey institute called Deloitte's revealed that only 44% of the millennial generation see that their work has a positive impact on society, 62% of the millennial generation consider work to be important to their identity, balance between work and life is something they prioritize. Millennials really appreciate working remotely and see the benefits. Three out of four respondents currently working in remote or combination jobs would consider looking for a new job if their company asked them to work full time at work. 39% of millennials say they always feel stressed or anxious at work. Financial concerns may hinder these efforts, with more than half of respondents saying it will become increasingly difficult or impossible to pay more for sustainable products and services if the economic situation remains the same or worsens.

Millennial workers have their own characteristics compared to workers from other generations. Millennial workers are workers born between 1981 and 1996 (Dimock, 2019). The characteristics inherent in millennial workers can have an impact on the companies that currently employ them, one of which is organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). OCB plays an important role in bridging personality, organizational commitment, job satisfaction and employee performance (Indarti et al., 2017). OCB was found to be able to improve performance and the effect was greater when social capital was included (Basu et al., 2017). In organizations with a high level of OCB, the level of employee sustainability performance will also be high (Jiang et al., 2017).

In millennial workers, OCB can be caused by various factors such as citizenship fatigue, organizational commitment, transformational leadership, organizational clan culture, psychological empowerment, leader-member exchange, proactive personality, work engagement, organizational justice, inclusive leadership, learning culture (Bolino et al., 2015; Devece et al., 2016; Farid et al., 2019; Jha, 2014; Kim, 2014; Newman et al., 2017; Tran & Choi, 2019). This research is aimed at finding out the impact that the dimensions of psychological empowerment have on OCB in the millennial generation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

It has been more than 30 years since (Organ, 1988) introduced the concept of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) which is defined as "individual behavior that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by formal reward systems, and in the aggregate promotes the effective

functioning of an organization.” OCB is characterized by individual behavior in the organization or extra-role behavior rather than predetermined responsibilities (Jha, 2014). OCB is behavior that is an individual choice and initiative, not related to the formal organizational reward system but in aggregate increases organizational effectiveness (Ali et al., 2022). OCB itself is divided into five dimensions such as conscientiousness, sportsmanship, courtesy, altruism, and civic virtue (de Geus et al., 2020).

Most of the early empirical research on OCB was directed at individual-level analysis and only then did researchers focus on identifying outcomes of OCB at the group level. (Podsakoff et al., 2014). Companies are starting to see employee behavior such as OCB as a way to achieve competitive advantage (Ocampo et al., 2018).

Psychological Empowerment

In a cognitive view, empowerment is an individual's assessment of the meaning (value of work), competence (ability to do work), self-determination (choices in initiating and managing actions), and impact (ability to influence organizational-related outcomes) (Jha, 2014).

In the aspects of psychological empowerment, impact is the most influential aspect followed by determination, meaning and competence on workforce agility (Muduli & Pandya, 2018). Previous researchers found a positive relationship between psychological empowerment and OCB (Jha, 2014; Saleem et al., 2017; Shapira- Lishchinsky & Benoliel, 2019). This research establishes the following research hypothesis:

- H₁: Meaning has a positive effect on OCB
- H₂: Competence has a positive effect on OCB
- H₃: Self-determination has a positive effect on OCB
- H₄: Impact has a positive effect on OCB

METHODOLOGY

This research method is quantitative causality. Data was taken from 100 millennial generation people via Google form using convenience sampling. Research data was taken over a period of time. Data were analyzed using the PLS SEM method. The psychological empowerment research instrument was adapted from (Spreitzer, 1995) with a total of 12 items, while for OCB it was adapted from (Tawil, 2022) with a total of 26 items.

RESEARCH RESULT

Respondent Description

The respondents of this study were 54 men (54%) and 46 women (46%). Respondents with high school/equivalent education totaled 5 people (5%), diploma numbered 3 people (3%), bachelor's degree/equivalent numbered 40 people (40%), master's degree numbered 50 people (50%), doctorate numbered 2 people (2%). A total of 66 people (66%) worked in the private sector, 11 people worked (11%) as civil servants, 8 people (8%) worked in state-owned companies, the remaining 15 people (15%) answered other. A total of 76 people

(76%) are permanent employees and 24 people (24%) are non-permanent employees. All respondents were born between 1981 and 1996 (millennial generation). The majority of respondents were male, had a master's degree, worked in the private sector and were permanent employees.

Validity test

Table 1. Validity Test

Variable	AVE	Decision
Meaning	0.732	Valid/accept
Competence	0.860	Valid/accept
Self-determination	0.774	Valid/accept
Impact	0.676	Valid/accept
OCB	0.507	Valid/accept

Table 1 indicates that all research variables are considered valid because they have an AVE (average variant extracted) value higher than 0.5. Affective commitment has an AVE score of 0.507. All dimensions of Psychological empowerment have an AVE score above 0.5. OCB has an AVE score above 0.5.

Table 2. The Value of Outer Loadings Psychological Empowerment

	ME		COM		SD		IM
PE1	0.825	PE4	0.945	PE7	0.907	PE10	0.881
PE2	0.887	PE5	0.962	PE8	0.886	PE11	0.900
PE3	0.855	PE6	0.874	PE9	0.845	PE12	0.664

Table 3. Outer Loadings OCB Value

	ALT		CON		SPO		COU		CIV
OCB1	0.658	OCB6	0.591	OCB11	0.667	OCB17	0.664	OCB22	0.631
OCB2	0.570	OCB7	0.599	OCB12	0.584	OCB18	0.838	OCB23	0.831
OCB3	0.523	OCB8	0.789	OCB13	0.765	OCB19	0.747	OCB24	0.814
OCB4	0.744	OCB9	0.839	OCB14	0.722	OCB20	0.758	OCB25	0.795
OCB5	0.792	OCB10	0.548	OCB15	0.666	OCB21	0.787	OCB26	0.578
				OCB16	0.832				

Tables 2 and 3 contain the outer loading values for each item from the psychological empowerment and OCB variables. Values of 0.5 and above remain included in further analysis as long as the AVE score is above 0.5 and the variable is declared valid. The outer loadings value of psychological empowerment ranges from 0.664 to 0.962. The OCB outer loadings value ranges from 0.523 to 0.839.

Table 4. Discriminant Validity

	COM	IM	ME	OCB	SD
COM	0.927				
IM	0.470	0.822			
ME	0.666	0.475	0.856		
OCB	0.596	0.570	0.518	0.712	
SD	0.599	0.480	0.495	0.373	0.880

Table 4 contains the results of discriminant validity using the Fornell-Larcker Criterion. The discriminant validity value of competence is 0.927 and is greater than the others (0.470; 0.666; 0.596; 0.599). The discriminant validity value of impact is 0.822 and is greater than the others. The discriminant validity value of meaning is 0.856 and is greater than the others. The discriminant validity value of self-determination is 0.880 and is greater than the others. The discriminant validity value of OCB is 0.712 and is greater than the others. This indicates that the constructs do not overlap between variables and each variable has its own characteristics in measuring its own construct.

Reliability Test

Table 5. Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability
Meaning	0.817	0.891
Competence	0.918	0.949
Self-determination	0.858	0.911
Impact	0.766	0.890
OCb	0.960	0.963

Table 5 shows the results of reliability testing shown through Cronbach's Alpha scores and composite reliability. All variables were found to have Cronbach's Alpha scores and composite reliability above 0.7 so that all research variable instruments were declared reliable and tended to be stable when used at different times.

R Square Test

The R square test results obtained were 0.477, which means that the dimensions of psychological empowerment contributed to the rise and fall of OCB by 47.7% and the remaining 52.3% was explained by other factors that were not in the research.

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing can be seen in the path coefficient image. The p value and t statistical value are used as the basis for decision making. The following will explain the image of the path coefficient related to the influence of psychological empowerment dimensions on OCB:

Figure 1. Path Coefficient

Figure 1 shows the T statistical value obtained on the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. The size of the original sample value, T statistic and P value will be explained in the next stage.

Table 6. Hypothesis Testing

	<i>Original Sample</i>	T Statistics	P Value	Decision
ME ► OCB	0.129	1.259	0.208	Rejected
COM ► OCB	0.400	3.187	0.001	Accepted
SD ► OCB	-0.110	1.070	0.285	Rejected
IM ► OCB	0.373	2.709	0.007	Accepted

Table 6 contains the results of hypothesis testing. The meaning and self-determination dimensions were found to have no impact on OCB. The dimensions of competence and impact were found to have a positive impact on OCB. Even though self-determination has no impact on OCB, it has a negative correlation direction (-0.110).

DISCUSSION

In this research, it was found that only two dimensions of psychological empowerment, such as competence and impact, were able to increase OCB. Meaning and self-determination have no impact on the rise and fall of OCB (Table 6). When employees have good abilities at work and feel that their existence has an impact on the company or organization, they will increasingly work voluntarily and above the average standards that apply in the company or organization. This is confirmed by previous research where when someone is competent in their work, their OCB level will increase (Sumarsi & Rizal, 2022). Workers who feel that what they do will have an impact on their organization tend to display OCB (Ertürk, 2022).

The results of other research reveal that the meaning dimension of the psychological empowerment variable is related to the dimensions of OCB such as conscientiousness, altruism and obedience. Apart from that, the competency dimension is also related to conscientiousness (Turnipseed & VandeWaa, 2020).

Overall, psychological empowerment provides positive support for increasing all dimensions of OCB (Wat & Shaffer, 2005). Psychological empowerment is positively related to OCB dimensions at the individual and organizational levels (Taylor, 2013). All dimensions of psychological empowerment are able to increase OCB, competence and meaning are the biggest factors in increasing workers' OCB (Shahri et al., 2015).

Overall, when the level of psychological empowerment of workers is high, the level of OCB will also be high (Saleem et al., 2017). Transformational leadership can make employees work beyond formal standards, especially for workers with high versus low psychological empowerment (Jha, 2014). Authentic leadership increases workers' psychological empowerment which ultimately increases OCB (Shapira- Lishchinsky & Benoliel, 2019). Psychological empowerment and work engagement are determining factors of job satisfaction, turnover intention, and employee OCB at the organizational level (Ginsburg et al., 2016). Psychological empowerment was found to have a positive and direct effect on OCB (Ghalavi & Nastiezaie, 2020). Psychological empowerment bridges the relationship between authentic leadership and core self-evaluations with OCB (Joo & Jo, 2017).

Organizations develop due to contributions made by leaders or subordinates (Jha, 2014). Factors such as gender, age, job design, work experience are related to OCB (Saleem et al., 2017). This means that in determining research respondents, it must not only focus on the millennial generation but must also be limited to gender, how long a person has worked, what the job characteristics are like.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research concludes that two dimensions of psychological empowerment, such as competence and impact, have a positive influence on OCB, while the other two dimensions, such as meaning and self-determination, have no influence on OCB.

This research is limited only by age, namely generation Y who were born from 1981 to 1996 without being limited by other backgrounds such as type of private or public organization, job characteristics, type of sector. Further research can limit these things apart from being limited in terms of age.

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